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Report

Uranium Series

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Type of report:

Results Report

Purpose:

Dating by uranium - thorium series

SUMMARY

The following report presents a summary of the dating results using the uranium series technique, requested by

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INTRODUCTION

Dating of four adhered crusts of siliceous rock and one calcareous rock is requested using uranium series analysis. The pieces are received on December 17, 2020, with the following coding:

ID	Aprox. quantity	Type of sample
TOR 20PR - 4000	g	Heterogeneous crust adhered to siliceous rock (quartzite)
TOR 20PR - 4001	g	Heterogeneous crust adhered to siliceous rock (quartzite)
TOR 20PR - 4002	g	Heterogeneous crust adhered to siliceous rock (quartzite)
TOR 20PR - 4003	g	Heterogeneous crust adhered to siliceous rock (quartzite)
TOR 20PR - 0001	g	Stalagmite slice with visible lamination

Some images of the samples and the location of the points selected for analysis can be consulted in Annex 1.

The laboratory coding is as follows:

User ID	Lab ID	Clean Lab ID
TOR20-PR-4000	20205-3	SU-477
TOR20-PR-4001	20205-4	SU-478
TOR20-PR-4002	20205-1	SU-475
TOR20-PR-4003	20205-2	SU-476
TOR20-PR-0001	20205-5	SU-479

Each of the specimens is subsampled, using a manual tungsten carbide bur, 0.8 mm in diameter. First, the most superficial part of the sampling area was removed with the drill itself, discarding it, and then an amount of between 10-50 mg of material was extracted, avoiding reaching the quartzite.

In the stalagmite, the furthest part of the growth zone, usually considered an open system, was chosen.

APPLIED METHODOLOGY

PREPARATION OF SAMPLE

The sampled materials are collected in low-density plastic centrifuge tubes and treated in a metal-free clean room, where radiotracers are added, homogenized, carbonate removed, digestion and separation of the analytes of interest using resins. ion exchange, following the internal PE-06SU method.

Once the uranium and thorium fractions of each sample have been separated and purified, the isotopic ratios and elemental concentration of the solutions obtained are determined, following the internal method PE-07SU.

INSTRUMENTATION

Measurements of isotopic ratios and quantification of uranium and thorium were performed using a dual-focus magnetic sector mass spectrometer, multi-collector detector system, and plasma ionization mode generated by inductive coupling MC ICP-MS Thermo NEPTUNE .

The equipment configuration included the use of an RPQ filter and detection of ^{238}U , ^{232}Th in Faraday cups and ^{230}Th and ^{234}Th in addition to the spikes ^{236}U , ^{229}Th , in ion counters. The equipment is configured with a jet interface system with type

RESULTS OBTAINED

The measurements of isotopic ratios and uranium and thorium content were carried out in two sequences per element in static and quantification by the standard bracketing method. The concentration of ²³⁸U and ²³²Th was carried out using the isotopic dilution method (IDMS). The spikes and standards used are gravimetrically obtained dilutions of standards and certified reference materials owned by CENIEH, with direct traceability to NIST and IRMM.

The numerical results obtained and the abbreviation legend are shown in Annex 2. An .xlsx file with the results tables is sent attached to this document, to facilitate its reading.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF THE RESULTS

The interpretation of the analytical results and translation into dating key has been carried out by applying the general radioactive decay equation and solving it using graphical methods. The agreement of the dates obtained graphically was checked by comparing them with those obtained using the Isoplot software. The decay constants and the results visualization scheme are those recommended by Prof. H. Cheng et al. (2013).

The results are compatible with the following minimum and maximum dating of the samples (table 1):

Table 1. Results of the dating of the samples received.

Sample	TOR20PR - 4000 <i>SU-20205-3</i>	TOR20PR - 4001 <i>SU-20205-4</i>	TOR20PR - 4002 <i>SU-20205-1</i>	TOR20PR - 4003 <i>SU-20205-2</i>	TOR20PR - 0001 <i>SU-20205-5</i>
Year	28 604	158 694	44 983	180 680	153 925
(1 σ)	(549)	(429)	(423)	(1 513)	(369)

Details of the analysis results are shown in Annex 2.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

H. Cheng, R. L. Edwards, C.C. Shen et al. (2013) Earth and Planetary Science Letters 371–372 82–91
M. Ivanovich and R. S. Harmon (eds.). Uranium-series Disequilibrium, 2nd edition. Oxford (Clarendon Press) 1992

REPORT SIGNATURE

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Sample TOR 20-Pr-4000

Description

Identification in laboratory: SU-2020-247-3

It is an amygdaloid biface type quartzite artifact measuring about 7x4 cm with a patina of carbonate material that can be analyzed to try to date it using uranium series.

The crust has low consistency and no lamellar structure is observed, while a certain porosity is sensed.

The following images show the complete specimen and details of the patina. The yellowish appearance with darker parts can be observed, suggesting the presence of components other than CaCO_3 , which are avoided as far as possible.

Sampling was carried out on the carbonate layer of the photograph, after removing the superficial part, taking a small amount without touching the biface.

Sample TOR 20-Pr-4001

Description

Identification in laboratory: SU-2020-247-4

It is an amygdaloid biface type quartzite artifact measuring about 10x5 cm with a patina of carbonate material that can be analyzed to try to date it using uranium series.

The following images show the complete specimen and details of the patina. The scab has low consistency and no lamellar structure is observed, and the yellowish appearance with darker parts can be observed, suggesting the presence of components other than CaCO_3 , which are avoided as much as possible.

Sampling was carried out on the carbonate layer of the photograph, after removing the superficial part, taking a small amount without touching the biface.

Sample TOR 20-Pr-4002

Description

Identification in laboratory: SU-2020-247-1

It is a quartzite flake measuring about 6x4 cm, with a carbonate crust attached. The thickness of this scab is variable, and can reach just over 1 mm in the thickest part.

The scab was sampled again after removing the most superficial part.

Sample TOR 20-Pr-4003

Description

Identification in laboratory: SU-2020-247-2

It is a quartzite core measuring about 3x3 cm with a yellowish crust and numerous black and red particles. The thickness reaches 1 mm in some places, although the appearance is quite heterogeneous.

Sample TOR 20-Pr-0001

Description

Identification in laboratory: SU-2020-247-5

This sample is a fragment of stalagmite. When cutting it, the evolution of this specimen is clearly observed.

For sampling, the central part of the stalagmite is avoided, taking the carbonate from the furthest part possible, as indicated by the arrow in the following photograph, and avoiding extracting carbonate from the most porous parts and those close to the edges.

ANNEX 2

DETAILS OF THE ANALYSIS

Table A1. Legend of the results table

Sample	Name of the sample collected.
Lab- ID	Code assigned to the collected sample.
SU-ID	Laboratory subsample code used to generate the data..
^{238}U [$\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$]	Uranium concentration in the subsample.
^{232}Th [$\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$]	Thorium concentration in the subsample .
$^{230}\text{Th}/^{232}\text{Th}$ $\times 10^{-6}$ [at/at]	Atomic ratio between isotopes of thorium, applied a factor of 10-6
$\delta^{234}\text{U}$ [med]	Relationship of activities between ^{234}U and ^{238}U , according to the following formula: $\delta^{234}\text{U} = ([^{234}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}] - 1) \times 1000$
$\delta^{234}\text{U}_{\text{nit}}$ [calc]	Value calculated according to the equation: $\delta^{234}\text{U}_{\text{init}} = \delta^{234}\text{U}_{\text{medida}} \times e^{\lambda(234)t}$ <p>Being t the age ^{230}Th calculated and corrected</p>
$^{230}\text{Th}/^{238}\text{U}$ [act/act]	Isotopic ratio between ^{230}Th and ^{238}U in terms of activities.
^{230}Th uncorr [y]	Calculated age, in years, according to Ivanovich & Harmon (1992), taking the year 1950 as a present reference.
^{230}Th corr [y]	Corrected age, in years, and referenced to 1950, by assuming an initial isotopic ratio $^{230}\text{Th}/^{232}\text{Th}$ (atomic) = $4.4 \pm 2.2 \times 10^{-6}$, as the typical values of a material in secular equilibrium, and taking the average value of the ratio between $^{232}\text{Th}/^{238}\text{U}$ = 3.8

Decay constants: $\lambda_{238} = 1.55125 \times 10^{-10}$; $\lambda_{234} = 2.82206 \times 10^{-6}$; $\lambda_{230} = 9.1705 \times 10^{-6}$

Table A1 Results of analysis by uranium series for the measured samples.

Sample	TOR 20 PR - 4000	TOR 20 PR – 4001	TOR 20 PR – 4002	TOR 20 PR - 4003	TOR 20 PR - 0001
Lab- Id	<i>SU-20205-3</i>	<i>SU-20205-4</i>	<i>SU-20205-1</i>	<i>SU-20205-2</i>	<i>SU-20205-5</i>
SU-ID	SU477	SU478	SU475	SU476	SU479
²³⁸ U	81.8	73.9	63.4	72.0	36.9
[μg g ⁻¹]	(0.008)	(0.002)	(0.004)	(0.007)	(0.001)
²³² Th	34.9	107.4	91.5	109.0	1.3
[μg g ⁻¹]	(0.1)	(1.9)	(0.2)	(0.8)	(0.1)
²³⁰ Th/ ²³² Th x10 ⁻⁶	22.5	26.1	10.3	24.0	1309
[at/at]	(0.01)	(0.02)	(0.02)	(0.02)	(2)
δ ²³⁴ U	984.8	1249.8	496.4	1004.2	2181
[med]	(0.2)	(1.2)	(0.07)	(0.09)	(3)
δ ²³⁴ U _{init}	1067.5	1955.9	563.6	1672.2	3367
[estimated]	(0.2)	(1.9)	(0.08)	(0.15)	(4)
²³⁰ Th/ ²³⁸ U	0.552	2.185	0.856	2.092	2.593
[act/act]	(0.008)	(0.002)	(0.004)	(0.007)	(0.0003)
²³⁰ Th	34569	210311	87296	264662	153925
[y]	(574)	(460)	(594)	(2772)	(1000)
²³⁰ Th corr	28604	158694	44983	180680	141406
[y]	(549)	(429)	(423)	(1513)	(369)

The values in parentheses indicate the uncertainties at level $\sigma = 1$ of the measurements in the same units as the result they accompany.